

Slurry conversion: A general method for formulating amorphous solid dispersions and fully integrating drug and polymer components

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Abstract. A solvent-sparing method, called “slurry conversion”, has been tested as a general approach to preparing amorphous solid dispersions (ASDs). In this method, a solid mixture of a drug and a polymer is stirred in the presence of a small quantity of a solvent, which is subsequently removed. In previous work, the method enabled more complete salt formation between lumefantrine (LMF), a basic antimalarial, with acidic polymers, than the common methods of hot melt extrusion and spray drying, leading to improved physical stability and release. Here we apply this method to 18 poorly soluble drugs formulated as binary and ternary ASDs. For a rigorous test, these drugs were formulated with a single polymer, poly(acrylic acid) (PAA), under the same condition: room temperature stirring in 1:1 ethanol-dichloromethane at 4:1 solvent/solid ratio. ASDs were prepared for 16 of the 18 drugs at 25% drug loading and 11 at 50% drug loading. The drugs that were not fully amorphized did not dissolve in the default solvent or crystallized during drying. For most drugs, an abrupt “clearing” of the slurry occurred during stirring, indicating complete dissolution and amorphization before drying. While clearing did not occur for some drugs (e.g., clofazimine), the product was still fully amorphous, through solvent-mediated conversion. For a basic drug, the degree of protonation by PAA increases smoothly with PAA concentration and is ordered by its basic strength, supporting the conclusion that the method allows the system to reach thermodynamic equilibrium. In addition to binary ASDs, ternary ASDs containing two drugs (LMF and artemether or LMF and artesunate) were successfully prepared to support applications in combination therapies. In these ternary formulations, the protonation of LMF follows the trend established for binary systems. We find that slurry conversion can be scaled up 60-fold from the typical batch size without any difficulties or adverse effect on the structure and properties of the product. Overall, our results demonstrate that slurry conversion is a general, low-cost, and green alternative to conventional methods for manufacturing ASDs where the components are fully integrated.

Keywords. Amorphous solid dispersion, poly(acrylic acid), slurry conversion, amorphous drug-polymer salts, degree of salt formation, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy.

Introduction

Solid oral dosage forms are traditionally formulated with the crystals of the active ingredients. Recent decades have seen significant growth in the development of amorphous solid dispersions (ASDs)^{1,2,3,4} to increase the bioavailability of poorly soluble drugs.^{5,6} Among the factors that account for this increased bioavailability are the higher solubility of an amorphous drug than its crystalline counterpart^{7,8} and the release of drug-containing nanoparticles that could facilitate absorption through a “reservoir” or “shuttle” effect.^{9,10,11}

An ASD is a multicomponent formulation, typically containing a drug, a polymer, and a surfactant, and can be manufactured in many ways.¹² Hot melt extrusion (HME),^{13,14} spray drying (SD),¹⁵ and freeze drying¹⁶ are commercially important methods. In addition, ASDs can be prepared by mechanical activation,¹⁷ rotary evaporation (RE),¹⁸ antisolvent precipitation (AP),^{19,20,21} and spray-freeze drying.²² These methods differ in solvent usage, processing temperature, equipment cost, and energy consumption. Since 2021, this laboratory has experimented with a simple method, called slurry conversion (SC), for ASD preparations,^{23,24,25,26} where solid ingredients are stirred in the presence of a small volume of a solvent, which is subsequently removed.

Given the many ways to prepare an ASD, many have investigated whether they produce the same product in terms of internal structure and pharmaceutical properties.^{27,28,29,30} Despite work in this area, the current understanding remains limited. We illustrate this situation using lumefantrine (LMF), a poorly soluble antimalarial, which has been formulated as ASDs by many groups in recent years.^{31,18,19,32,25,26,33,34} LMF is a basic drug, and Figure 1 shows its degree of protonation when formulated with an acidic polymer, poly(acrylic acid) (PAA), by various methods.²⁵ The degree of protonation is a direct probe of how well the drug has been mixed and reacted with the polymer. We observe a large difference between the ASDs prepared by the different methods. At 40% drug loading, the degree of protonation ranges from almost zero for an ASD prepared by HME³¹ to 85% for that prepared by SC.²⁵ For this drug, the degree of protonation directly impacts its physical stability and dissolution performance. The large difference shown in Figure 1 is also observed for LMF formulated with other acidic polymers,²⁶ highlighting the common occurrence of a potentially widespread problem.

Figure 1. Degree of LMF protonation by PAA in formulations prepared by different methods. At a fixed drug concentration, the different methods reached very different degrees of protonation. Adapted from Figures 5 and 6 in Ref 25.

In this work, we evaluate the generality of the slurry conversion method for formulating ASDs, both binary and ternary, and its ability to control drug-polymer salt formation. In previous work,²⁶ LMF was formulated with different polymers, and here we investigate various drugs (Scheme 1) formulated with the same polymer PAA. All drugs selected are poorly water soluble (BCS Class II or IV)^{35,36} and have varying basic strengths for testing the completion of their salt formation with the acidic polymer PAA. For a strong test of the method, a single synthesis condition^{25,26} was employed for the different drugs at fixed temperature, solvent, and solvent/solid ratio. We find that slurry conversion can prepare ASDs for most drugs tested (16/18 at 25% drug loading and 11/18 at 50% drug loading). For a given drug, the degree of salt formation varies smoothly with the PAA concentration and correlates with its basic strength, supporting the conclusion that slurry conversion enables full interaction between the drug and the polymer. In addition to binary formulations, ternary ASDs containing multiple drugs were investigated to test the ability to prepare combination therapies, an increasingly utilized approach for treating infections.³⁷ We find that LMF can be formulated as ternary ASDs with artemether and artesunate – standard combinations for treating malaria, where LMF is protonated to a degree expected from the trend for binary ASDs. These findings demonstrate that slurry conversion is a versatile, low-cost, and green alternative to the conventional methods for ASD manufacturing.

Scheme 1. Structures of poly(acrylic acid) (PAA) and the drugs used in this work: lumefantrine (LMF), terfenadine (TFD), clofazimine (CFZ), pretomanid (PTM), itraconazole (ITZ), ketoconazole (KTZ), loratadine (LTD), felodipine (FDP), ritonavir (RTV), nevirapine (NVP), mebendazole (MBZ),

pyrimethamine (PMA), albendazole (ABZ), carbamazepine (CBZ), indapamide (IDP), efavirenz (EFZ), artemether (ATM), and artesunate (ATS).

Materials & Methods

Materials. Poly(acrylic acid) (MW = 450,000 g/mol), albendazole, clofazimine, erythromycin, indapamide, loratadine, mebendazole, and terfenadine were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO), nevirapine from Ambeed, Inc. (Arlington Heights, IL), carbamazepine from Alfa Aesar (Haverhill, MA), felodipine from J&K Scientific (San Jose, CA), and pyrimethamine from MP Biomedicals (Solon, OH). Itraconazole, ketoconazole, and lumefantrine were purchased from VWR International (Radnor, PA). Pretomanid was gifted by TB Alliance (Pretoria, South Africa) and artemether and artesunate by Nanjing Bilatchem Industrial Co., Ltd. (Nanjing, China). Dichloromethane (DCM) (ChromAR grade) was purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific (Fair Lawn, NJ), and ethanol from Decon Laboratories (King of Prussia, PA). All materials were used as received.

Slurry Synthesis. The condition for slurry synthesis of ASDs has been described previously.²⁶ In brief, the drug and polymer powders were mixed at 25 or 50 wt% drug loading and dichloromethane (DCM) and ethanol (EtOH) at 1:1 volume ratio were added in sequence to reach a 4:1 (w/w) solvent/solid ratio in the slurry. Each mixture was stirred with a magnetic stir bar at room temperature for up to 30 minutes and was dried under vacuum at room temperature for one day. During drying, the rapid loss of solvent caused the viscous solution to boil and rise, forming a brittle, glassy foam that was ground in an agate mortar with a pestle to a powder.

To investigate the ability to scale up the slurry synthesis, the batch size was enlarged from the standard size of 0.4 g of total solids (the drug plus the polymer) to up to 25 g. The scale-up process employed the same solvent, solvent/solid ratio, and drying condition as described above. A 20 mL glass vial was used to house the reaction mixture at the 0.4 g scale; a 250 mL glass bottle was used at the 25 g scale. To facilitate mixing at a larger scale, a Polytron PT 1200 E Handled Homogenizer was used in place of a magnetic stirrer.

Powder X-Ray Diffraction (PXRD). PXRD was performed with a Bruker D8 Advance X-ray diffractometer with a Cu K α source operating at a tube load of 40 kV and 40 mA. A powder sample of approximately 10 mg was spread and flattened on a Si (510) zero-background holder and scanned between 3° and 40° (2 θ) at a step size of 0.02° and a scan rate of 1 s/step. For a partially crystalline sample, % crystallinity was calculated by dividing the area of the crystalline peaks by the total area of the crystalline peaks and the amorphous halo, treating the amorphous halo as a broad peak. Peak integration was performed using the program EVA from Bruker-AXS. This procedure provides an estimate of the crystalline fraction in a sample. A more accurate determination could be made using a calibration curve constructed from the PXRD patterns of samples of known crystalline fractions, but this was not pursued in this work.

X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS). The details of XPS measurement and data analysis have been described previously.³⁸ For each pure drug and ASD sample, approximately 5 mg of powder was pressed onto a carbon tape affixed to the XPS sample holder. The high-resolution spectrum of the N atom was used to measure the protonated fraction of an amine drug. For drugs containing a single nitrogen, a two-Gaussian fitting was performed using the program Origin following smart baseline subtraction. For drugs containing multiple nitrogen atoms, the protonated fraction was obtained using a curve subtraction method (see Results & Discussion). For each sample, spectra were recorded in duplicate (two separate regions) and averaged.

Results and Discussion

We first describe the results on binary ASDs to highlight the success rate of amorphization and trends in salt formation and then the findings on ternary ASDs containing multiple drugs.

Slurry Synthesis Amorphization Success Rate and Clearing Transition. In this work, different drugs (Scheme 1) were formulated with PAA at 25% and 50% drug loading (DL) under the same condition (room temperature stirring in 1:1 DCM-EtOH at 4:1 solvent/solid ratio). Table 1 summarizes the systems investigated and the success rate for slurry conversion to prepare amorphous solid dispersions. In this table, the crystallinity of the dried formulations is shown where zero signifies an amorphous product and a non-zero value indicates the crystalline fraction of the drug determined by PXRD (Figure 2). For comparison, Figure 2 also shows the PXRD patterns of the crystalline raw materials and the reference patterns generated from single-crystal structures to demonstrate their phase purity.^{39,40,41,42,43,44,45,46,47,48,49,50,51,52,53,54,55,56}

Table 1. Amorphization success rates of binary drug-PAA ASDs by slurry conversion. Crystallinity of each dried formulation is given with zero signifying an amorphous product. DL: drug loading.

<i>Drug</i>	<i>MW (g/mole)</i>	<i>Crystallinity of dried formulation</i>	
		<i>25% DL</i>	<i>50% DL</i>
Clofazimine (CFZ)	473.4	0	0
Lumefantrine (LMF)	528.9	0	0
Terfenadine (TFD)	471.7	0	0
Carbamazepine (CBZ)	236.3	0	0
Efavirenz (EFZ)	315.7	0	0
Indapamide (IDP)	365.8	0	0
Albendazole (ABZ)	265.3	12%	15%
Felodipine (FDP)	383.1	0	0
Itraconazole (ITZ)	705.6	0	0
Ketoconazole (KTZ)	531.4	0	6%
Loratadine (LTD)	382.9	0	0
Mebendazole (MBZ)	295.3	16%	25%
Nevirapine (NVP)	266.3	0	26%
Pyrimethamine (PMA)	248.7	0	10%
Pretomanid (PTM)	359.3	0	31%
Ritonavir (RTV)	720.9	0	0
Artemether (ATM)	298.4	0	93%
Artesunate (ATS)	384.4	0	0

Figure 2. PXR D patterns of binary drug-PAA formulations prepared using the slurry method at 25 and 50% drug loading (DL), along with the patterns for the pure crystalline drugs as starting materials and their reference patterns generated from the single-crystal structures deposited in CCDC under the refcodes supplied.³⁸⁻⁵⁵ Most formulations were fully amorphous and a few partially crystalline.

Table 1 and Figure 2 show that for most drugs investigated, the slurry method successfully rendered the initially crystalline drug amorphous (zero crystallinity). Of the 18 drugs, 16 were amorphized at 25% DL and 11 at 50% DL. The decrease of the amorphization rate with DL is expected since less polymer is available to interact with the drug and prevent its crystallization. The drugs tested cover a wide range of structures and therapeutic classes, indicating a wide applicability of the slurry conversion method for formulating ASDs.

Our survey of the 18 drugs indicate that the drugs of higher molecular weights (MW) are more likely to be amorphized. We can see this result by examining Table 1; Figure 3 shows the result more clearly by plotting the crystallinity of each dried formulation against the MW of the drug. The partially crystalline formulations are mainly associated with the drugs of lower MW. At MW > 350 g/mol, amorphization was successful in all but one case (ketoconazole at 50% DL, with 6% crystallinity). This result is not surprising because smaller molecules tend to crystallize faster than larger ones. In addition, at a fixed drug loading, a lower-MW drug has higher mole fraction and higher chemical potential (assuming ideal mixing), leading to higher a driving force of crystallization. Crystallization could occur in the drying step even if the drug was fully dissolved in the solvent with the polymer (see below).

Figure 3. Crystallinity of dried formulations at 25% and 50% DL plotted against the drug's molecular weight. Zero crystallinity indicates an amorphous formulation. Low molecular-weight drugs tend to remain partially crystalline in the dried product.

A notable feature of the slurry synthesis is that for most drugs investigated, the initially turbid slurry abruptly “cleared” after a few minutes of stirring, forming a transparent, viscous solution. This transition was a useful visual indicator of complete dissolution and amorphization of the initially crystalline drug, before the drying step to lock in the amorphous structure. Figure 4a illustrates this clearing transition using LMF-PAA. The slurry remained turbid for several minutes and suddenly cleared with an increase of viscosity, sometimes halting the rotation of the stir bar. This transition provides an efficient screening tool for identifying drug-polymer combinations suitable for slurry conversion, but as we show below with CFZ, complete clearing is not a necessary condition for amorphization.

Of the drugs tested, three did not show the clearing transition: CFZ, ABZ, and MBZ. As Figure 4b shows, the CFZ slurry remained opaque during stirring and contained residual solids, but a

pronounced color change occurred from red to black, indicating the reaction between CFZ and PAA (salt formation).²³ Despite the lack of clearing, subsequent drying of the CFZ slurry yielded a fully amorphous solid (Figure 2). This example illustrates that even without full clearing (dissolution), the drug and the polymer could still interact, transforming the initially crystalline drug to an amorphous solid dispersion, as in a solution-mediated polymorphic transformation. The red-to-black color change of the CFZ slurry is a result of the protonation of CFZ's imine group and its effect on the π -electron system.²³

Figure 4. Clearing transition during slurry conversion. (a) Typical progression illustrated with LMF-PAA, where a turbid slurry turns into a clear solution and dries to an amorphous solid. (b) Atypical behavior illustrated with CFZ-PAA, where the slurry did not fully clear. Despite this, the CFZ-PAA slurry dried to an amorphous product.

Similar to CFZ, the slurries of ABZ and MBZ did not clear, but unlike CFZ, their dried slurries were partially crystalline (Table 1). This was the result of the low solubility of these drugs in the default solvent and their relatively low basicity to react with PAA. It was possible to fully dissolve ABZ and MBZ in an alternative solvent (DMSO) at an elevated temperature of 75°C, but the high boiling point of DMSO made the subsequent drying difficult. It is of interest to further optimize the method to prepare ASDs of these challenging drugs.

Salt Formation. Previous work has shown that for an ASD of lumefantrine and an acidic polymer, the degree of salt formation depends strongly on the method of manufacturing, and in turn, influences its physical stability and release kinetics.^{18,25,26} Following the previous work, we use the degree of salt formation here as a probe of the internal structure of an ASD and a metric for comparing different formulation methods. Figure 5 shows the XPS N spectra collected for this purpose. For the drugs of this study, the potential salt formation involves the protonation of a nitrogenous base by PAA, thus altering its XPS N spectrum. In Figure 5, the top two panels correspond to the two aliphatic amines (TFD and LMF), the next three panels to the aromatic amines (LTD, NVP, and FDP), and the bottom panel to an amide (CBZ). In this order, the drug's

basic strength decreases, and so should the degree of protonation by PAA. For the weakest bases, little or no protonation is expected, but there could be spectral change due to the formation of stronger hydrogen bonds between the drug and PAA than between the drug molecules. These expectations are broadly confirmed by the observed spectra. For LMF and TFD, the N spectrum shifts to higher binding energy (BE), by about 2 eV, indicating the protonation of the aliphatic amine by PAA.²⁵ For the other drugs, the peak shifts are smaller. For CBZ, the shift is barely visible, consistent with its lack of basicity and the peak shift could be a result of stronger hydrogen bonds between CBZ and PAA than between CBZ molecules, without proton exchange.

Figure 6 shows the degree of protonation for a given drug as a function of DL. The data on LMF²⁵ and CFZ²³ are from the previous work in this lab and the other data are from this work. If the drug has a single basic nitrogen atom (e.g., LMF, TFD, and FDP), the observed spectrum is fitted as a sum of two Gaussian functions that represent the unprotonated and the protonated N atoms and their relative areas yield the degree of protonation.²⁵ For LTD, NVP, and CBZ, there are multiple nitrogen atoms in the molecule and only one of them is expected to interact strongly with PAA (the amide N, for example, is expected to be inert). For these drugs, a subtraction method was used.

As illustrated in Figure 7 for LTD, the spectrum of the pure drug is first scaled to have the same area A_0 as that of the ASD spectrum and then subtracted from the ASD spectrum. The positive area ΔA in the subtracted spectrum corresponds to the increase of protonated nitrogen atoms and the negative area to the loss of unprotonated nitrogen atoms. Dividing ΔA by the area that represents one nitrogen atom ($A_0/2$, where 2 is the number of nitrogen atoms per LTD molecule) gives the fraction of protonation. The subtraction procedure removes the signal from the non-reactive nitrogen atom (amide) and isolates the change due to salt formation. This method avoids the otherwise complex peak fitting process to account for both reactive and non-reactive nitrogen atoms.

Figure 5. XPS N spectra of drug-PAA ASDs prepared by slurry synthesis (solid curves) and the corresponding pure drugs (dashed curves). 25 wt% drug loading for all ASDs.

Figure 6 shows that for each drug, the extent of drug-polymer salt formation smoothly decreases with DL. This is sensible because as the drug concentration increases, more drug molecules compete for the same reaction site on PAA, at lower probability of success. When compared at the same DL, the different drugs show different degrees of interaction and the overall ranking agrees with that of their basic strengths: aliphatic amine (LMF and TFD) and imine (CFZ) > aromatic amine (LTD, NVP, and FDP) > amide (CBZ). LMF and TFD are similar ternary aliphatic amines, and it is sensible that both are similarly protonated by PAA at the same DL. For the weaker bases CBZ and FDP, the N atom peak shift observed may have large contributions from hydrogen bonding between the drug and PAA, and the precise breakdown between proton transfer and hydrogen bonding requires further analysis.

Figure 6. Degree of protonation as a function of drug loading for 6 drugs formulated with PAA. The degree of protonation increases with decreasing drug loading (increasing PAA concentration) and basic strength.

The salt-formation results observed here (Figure 6) are not surprising from the standpoint of acid-base equilibrium, but noteworthy given the known difficulty to complete salt formation in a drug-polymer ASD (Figure 1). For LMF, the degree of salt formation with an acidic polymer varies significantly with the method of preparation.^{18,19,25,26} This variability can be attributed to the difficulty of a sluggish macromolecule to fully react with a small molecule. Of the various methods compared in Figure 1, slurry conversion outperforms the others in completing the salt formation (Figure 1),²⁶ and the result of this study supports this conclusion. If the method had difficulty in completing the drug-polymer reaction, the data in Figure 6 would not form the smooth trends expected from acid-base equilibrium.

Figure 7. Subtraction method for determining the degree of protonation when non-reactive N atoms are present, illustrated for LTD.

Ternary Formulations. Of the 48 ASD products FDA-approved between 2012 and 2023, 18 were fixed-dose combinations (FDCs) to facilitate patient compliance and synergy between drugs.⁵⁷ Coartem® (lumefantrine-artemether) exemplifies an FDC for malaria⁵⁸ and Kaletra® (lopinavir-ritonavir) an FDC for AIDS. We investigated whether slurry conversion can prepare multi-drug ASDs for applications in this area. We used lumefantrine-artemether (LMF-ATM) and lumefantrine-artesunate (LMF-ATS) as models, and to connect with the results on binary systems, used PAA as the formulation polymer. Table 2 summarizes the ternary formulations prepared and the success rate of amorphization. These formulations contained LMF and a partner drug (ATM or ATS) at two ratios (1:1 and 6:1) and two DLs (25 and 50%). The 6:1 drug ratio was chosen because the clinically important Coartem contains LMF and ATM at this ratio. For these ternary systems, the DL refers to the total amount of the drugs in the formulation.

Table 2. Amorphization success rate of ternary ASDs prepared by slurry conversion. PAA is the dispersion polymer. The 6:1 ratio was chosen to match the composition in Coartem®.

Drug A	Drug B	A:B Ratio (w/w)	Crystallinity of dried formulation	
			25% DL (A+B)	50% DL (A+B)
Lumefantrine (LMF)	Artemether (ATM)	1:0	0	0
		6:1	0	0
		1:1	0	0
		0:1	0	93%
Lumefantrine (LMF)	Artesunate (ATS)	1:0	0	0
		6:1	0	0
		1:1	0	0
		0:1	0	0

Table 2 indicates that all the ternary formulations prepared were amorphous (zero crystallinity) and the PXRD patterns that support this conclusion are collected in Figure 8. All the ternary formulations showed broad and featureless PXRD patterns, without the sharp crystalline diffraction peaks present in the raw starting materials (bottom of Figure 8), indicating their amorphous nature. At the bottom of Figure 8 are also given the PXRD patterns generated from the single-crystal structures deposited in CCDC, which verify the phase purity of each crystalline starting material. Between ATM and ATS, ATM is the faster crystallizer since in the binary formulation with PAA (50% DL), ATM is partially crystalline (93%), but ATS is fully amorphous. However, in the ternary formulations of ATM, LMF, and PAA, ATM is fully amorphous (Table 2). This highlights that the presence of LMF helps inhibit the crystallization of ATM.

As in the case of most binary ASDs prepared, all ternary formulations tested exhibited an abrupt clearing transition where the turbid slurry became transparent (Figure 4a), indicating dissolution of the crystalline drug before the drying step. The inclusion of a second drug had no significant effect on the clearing behavior. This suggests that the clearing transition is a generic feature of slurry conversion independent of the number of chemical components present and can be used as a general screening tool for systems suitable for this approach.

XPS was used to determine the degree of salt formation between LMF and PAA in the ternary formulations, for comparison with the trend observed with the binary formulations (Figure 1). Figure 9 shows the XPS N spectra for the ternary ASDs prepared. Each of these spectra features a strong peak corresponding to protonated N atoms, and a small peak at lower BE corresponding to unprotonated N atoms is visible with only two formulations with high LMF concentrations (50% DL). This indicates complete or nearly complete protonation of LMF by PAA in these ternary ASDs.

Figure 10 shows the degree of protonation of LMF in the ternary ASDs calculated from the XPS spectra in Figure 9 using the same method described above. For comparison, the previous results on the binary ASDs composed of LMF and PAA are also included. In this plot, the degree of protonation of LMF is plotted against its concentration in the ASD, be it binary or ternary. We find that the data points for the ternary ASDs conform well with the trend for the binary ASDs. This result indicates that the second drug (ATM or ATS), at the concentration used, has a minor effect on the acid-base reaction between LMF and PAA. Of the two partner drugs with LMF, ATM is neutral and ATS is acidic (Scheme 1), and the fact that there is little difference in their effect on the LMF-PAA reaction indicates that they are mostly inert bystanders, perhaps because PAA has far higher acidic group density than ATS in the formulations prepared. This result may be useful for predicting the degree of salt formation in multicomponent ASDs if the polymer supplies most of the reaction sites.

Figure 8. PXRD patterns of ternary ASDs prepared by slurry conversion, along with those of the crystalline drugs and the reference patterns generated from the single-crystal structures deposited in CCDC under the refcodes supplied. All ternary ASDs prepared were amorphous.

Figure 9. XPS N spectra of ternary ASDs. The peak at higher BE corresponds to the protonated N atom of LMF; the peak at lower BE to the unprotonated N atom.

Figure 10. Degree of protonation of LMF by PAA in binary (circles) and ternary (other symbols) ASDs vs % LMF in the formulation. The data on binary and ternary ASDs fall on a common trend.

Scale Up of Slurry Conversion.

To assess the ability to scale up the slurry synthesis, we used the LMF-PAA formulation as a model and increased the batch size from the standard 0.4 g to up to 25 g. The process at larger scale employed the same solvent, solvent/solid ratio, and drying condition as the standard process. To facilitate mixing, a handheld homogenizer was used in place of a magnetic stirrer. We found that the process could be scaled up without any difficulties or any adverse effect on the structure and properties of the product. At the larger scale, the same clearing transition was observed where the initially turbid slurry abruptly became a transparent and viscous solution; see the picture in Figure 11a for a cleared slurry at the 25 g scale. Figure 11a compares the PXRD patterns of the dried products obtained by slurry synthesis at the 0.4 g and 25 g scales. Both materials are amorphous, showing no crystalline diffraction peaks. Figure 11b shows the XPS nitrogen spectra of the two formulations.

These spectra indicate that LMF was highly protonated in the ASDs and the degrees of protonation were both at 87%. These results demonstrate that the slurry synthesis can be readily performed at increased scales. This work has successfully increased the batch size 60-fold, and further work is warranted to explore further scale up on industrial processing equipment.

Conclusions

This study investigated the generality of slurry conversion (SC) as a low-cost, solvent-sparing method to synthesize amorphous solid dispersions (ASDs) of poorly soluble drugs. To complement a previous study where the method was used to formulate the same drug (lumefantrine) with different polymers,²⁶ here it is applied to formulate multiple drugs with the same polymer (PAA). For a rigorous test, 18 drugs (Scheme 1) were formulated under a single condition: room temperature stirring and 1:1 ethanol-DCM as solvent at 4:1 solvent/solid ratio. We find a high success rate of amorphization (ASD formation): 16/18 at 25% drug loading and 11/18 at 50% drug

Figure 11. (a) PXRD patterns of LMF-PAA formulations at 50% drug loading prepared by slurry conversion at two batch sizes: 0.4 g (top) and 25 g (bottom). The inset shows the 25 g scale slurry after clearing, before drying to a solid product. (b) XPS N spectra of the two formulations in (a). The peak at higher BE corresponds to the protonated N atom of LMF; the peak at lower BE to the unprotonated N atom. Both formulations show 87% protonation.

loading. Of the 18 drugs, only ABZ and MBZ failed outright, for their insolubility in the default solvent and fast crystallization. Overall, the high success rate of this simple method is encouraging. Using LMF as a model, this work has shown that the slurry synthesis can be scaled up 60-fold without any difficulties or any adverse effect on the structure and properties of the product. We highlight that the method has very low equipment cost, lower solvent usage than other solvent-based methods, and low energy consumption. This method permits rapid screening of candidate formulations in early development and has the potential to be a general platform for ASD manufacturing.

Using XPS, we have characterized the degree of salt formation between a drug and PAA in an ASD. The strongest bases (CFZ, an imine, and LMF and TFD, two aliphatic amines) were protonated to the greatest extent, followed by LTD and FDP (aromatic amines) and by CBZ (amide). For each drug, the degree of protonation smoothly decreases with increasing drug loading, a consequence of more molecules competing for the same reaction site at lower probability of success. Both results are expected for an acid-base reaction at equilibrium and support the conclusion that slurry conversion allows the ASD ingredients to fully mix and react. Had it failed to do so, we would expect erratic results of salt formation as illustrated in Figure 1, without smooth and meaningful trends. Although slurry conversion was first used to synthesize amorphous drug-polymer salts,^{23,24} its success with basic drugs of different strengths and an acidic drug (ATS) indicates its applicability for synthesizing neutral ASDs.

The physical state of the drug and the polymer in the slurry deserves attention as it influences how the components interact during synthesis and the ASD structure after drying. The often observed clearing transition (Figure 4a) indicates full dissolution of the components in the slurry solvent and amorphization of the initially crystalline drug. For salt-forming systems, the drug and the polymer are likely organized as ion pairs in the organic slurry solvent and remain as such during drying to a solid. Unlike water, an organic solvent is less capable of stabilizing isolated ions by solvation. Elucidating the state of the drug and the polymer in the slurry could help understand and control the resulting ASD structures.

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TOC graphic

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